

" MAIN DIALECTS IN GREAT BRITAIN"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6564059>

Rozmetov Og'abek Ergash o'g'li

Graduate student of Uzbekistan State World Languages University, The Faculty of English Philology

Annotation: *The phonetic peculiarities of British dialects are investigated in this essay. The goal of the article is to shed light on some of the main dialects and their typical features in terms of lexis and phonetics.*

Keywords: *dialect, slang, received pronunciation, Standard English*

English is a language that is spoken by millions of people over the globe. Not surprisingly, there are variations of it depending on the geographical location, the people who speak it as a first or second language and the culture. In Great Britain alone, there are almost 40 dialects of English. However, in this article, I will be focusing on the predominant ones and they are:

1. Geordie

People from Newcastle speak a dialect called Geordie, which is one of the strongest and most distinctive accents in England. Geordie changes all the rules of Standard English, so nothing is pronounced as you'd expect it to be: the word button would be pronounced BOT-tdan instead of BUH-tun, with a 'ooh' sound on the letter U and a rolled T.

2. Yorkshire

One of the biggest counties in England, Yorkshire has a distinctive accent where one of the biggest pronunciation differences is on the letter U, which is spoken as ooo rather than uh – so cut is pronounced coht and blood is pronounced blohd. Yorkshire dialect is mainly spoken in cities like York, Leeds and Sheffield.

3. Welsh

Officially a different country, Wales has a culture and language of its own that's spoken by half a million people. They have brilliantly long and complicated words like Llanfairpwllgwyngyllgogerychwyrndrobwllllantysiliogogoch, which is the name of a Welsh village (and the second longest place name in the world). When Welsh people speak English, their accent is instantly recognizable – they pronounce words like 'Wales' as WEE-alls unlike the English, who pronounce it WAY-ells.

4. Brummie

The name is derived from Brummagem and Bromwichham, both historical alternate names for the large city of Birmingham, where people speak this dialect.

People with a Brummie accent would say the word ‘hello’ as heh-LOUW instead of HEH-low, although there are lots of variations of the accent across the city.

5. West Country

The West Country includes the counties of Gloucestershire, Dorset, Somerset, Devon and Cornwall, and the dialect is the closest to the old British language of Anglo-Saxon, which was rooted in Germanic languages – so, true West Country speakers say I be instead of I am, and Thou bist instead of You are, which is very close to Ich bin (I am) and Du bist (You are) in modern German. The rest of the accent is rhotic (where the letter R is soft and rolled), so it actually sounds a bit like American English, although West Country residents won’t admit to that. This accent is mainly spoken in some of the major West Country cities, like Bristol or Bournemouth.

6. R.P.

The accent of the Home Counties area (the counties of Berkshire, Buckinghamshire, Hertfordshire, Kent, Surrey, and Sussex) is closest to what people call Queen’s English, also known as Received Pronunciation (R.P.) or Standard English. It’s basically a ‘flat’ accent with emphasised vowels like A (pronounced ah as in car) and O (pronounced ohw as in snow) but often varied pronunciation between different words, which you’ll find tricky if you’re learning English for the first time: words like cough and dough are spelled almost the same but spoken differently. It is mainly spoken in cities like Oxford, Cambridge, Eastbourne and Brighton.

7. Cockney

Perhaps the most famous British accent other than R.P. is Cockney. It developed as the dialect of the poorer working classes in the East End of London, and it’s still regarded as a marker of ‘true’ East London heritage. Like the Essex accent, Cockney swaps the th sound for f, drops the h in front of words like head, and elongates vowels like A and E. However, perhaps it’s most famous for Cockney Rhyming Slang, where people replace words with another word that’s an abbreviation of an unrelated phrase that rhymes with it: like dog (as in ‘dog and bone’) to mean telephone.

LITERATURE:

1. <https://www.ef.com/wwen/blog/language/british-dialects-you-need-to-know/>
2. Wells, John C. (1982), *Accents of English, Volume 2: The British Isles* (pp. i–xx, 279–466), Cambridge University Press
3. Bailey, George (2018), "Emerging from below the social radar: Incipient evaluation in the North West of England", *Journal of Sociolinguistics*
4. *A Dictionary of North East Dialect*, 2004, Northumbria University Press, ISBN 1-904794-16-5
5. Pearce, Michael (2012). "Folk accounts of dialect differences in Tyne and Wear". *Dialectologia et Geolinguistica*

6. Tidholm, Hans (1983). "The Dialect of Egton in North Yorkshire".
Language
7. Bill Griffiths: A Dictionary of North East Dialect, 2004, Northumbria
University Press